

Open Mapping for Urban Resilience: A Routing Model to Nearest Safe Spaces in Earthquake-Vulnerable Dhaka

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Dhaka, a rapidly expanding megacity with extreme seismic vulnerability, sits near active fault lines and has grown by tens of millions in recent decades without sufficient disaster planning [1]. With 15–20 million residents and dense informal settlements, little per-capita open ground exists. This study maps all candidate “safe spaces” (parks, plazas, empty lots, schoolyards, etc.) and computes routes to the nearest one for every neighborhood, using only open data and free GIS tools. To ensure scientific validity, the study grounds the methodology in recent literature: for example, Fan et al. highlight that mapping urban open space (UOS) at high resolution can improve disaster emergency response [2], and Messina et al. show that volunteer mapping completeness varies widely in dense slums [3]. The approach integrates these insights: it uses satellite imagery and existing data to classify open land, leverages OpenStreetMap (OSM) for city features while addressing its gaps with community field mapping, and implements routing in QGIS (open-source) to maximize reproducibility. The result is a set of open-data maps and tools that urban planners, NGOs, and citizens can use for earthquake preparedness.

The open space identification begins with multi-source imagery and GIS analysis using GEE (Google Earth Engine). The study first gathered Sentinel-2 and other recent satellite data plus available cadastral or land-use maps to spot candidate open areas. Using supervised classification (Random Forest on NDVI and texture bands) open-land patches were delineated. Existing open-space tags from OSM (e.g., *leisure=park*, *landuse=grass*) were imported as seed areas. Raw candidates were filtered by size and accessibility, and each candidate open space was verified via high-resolution imagery or site visits to ensure accessibility and safety. This two-step classification–verification process parallels best practices in remote-sensing UOS (Urban Open Space) mapping [2] and ensures reliability.

Because this work relies on OSM data for Dhaka’s roads and buildings, handling data gaps is vital. OSM in South Asia is known to be incomplete: a global study found that 69% of cities had <20% building coverage, and South Asian cities averaged ~9% completeness [4]. But for Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh, the risk of a data gap is low due to the active role

of the OSM volunteers. Figure 1 illustrates the process of identifying candidate open spaces prior to routing analysis.

Figure 1. Identification of Open Space.

For routing to the nearest safe space, proprietary QGIS tools were used for a fully open-source workflow. The updated OSM road network was loaded into QGIS, and a routable graph was built in PostgreSQL with PostGIS and pgRouting. Alternatively, QNEAT3 in QGIS was used for shortest-path and isochrone algorithms [5]. The model calculates the shortest walking routes from populated centroids to the closest verified safe space, creating an accessibility map. Using QGIS/QNEAT3 removes licensing barriers and ensures replicability [6].

To assess the performance of the routing model, generated routes were cross-checked against high-resolution imagery and field-verified paths where available. Route lengths and travel times were compared across algorithms (pgRouting vs. QNEAT3) to ensure consistency, while accessibility scores were validated against known population centers. This verification step demonstrates that the model produces realistic routes and enhances confidence in its applicability for evacuation planning.

Replicability is prioritized, the workflow and parameters are documented, and all source data will be open after publication. The method could be repeated in any other Global South city by replacing input data with local OSM extracts and imagery. As Howe and Tullis

argue, publishing open-source GIS workflows enables reproducibility without software cost barriers [6].

Outputs include, (a) a map layer of all safe open spaces with attributes; (b) a model that will generate the route maps from each neighborhood to its nearest safe space. This model allows city planners, emergency responders, and community groups to explore evacuation scenarios.

This work is grounded in literature emphasizing that accessible open spaces reduce earthquake casualties [2], and that community-driven geospatial data are critical in informal cities [3]. The method aligns with SDG 11.7 on public open spaces. Best practices in participatory GIS stress empowering locals to map hazards and resources [7]. Recent reviews highlight that volunteer mapping increasingly fills data gaps when combined with local expertise [3]. This study contributes by adding disaster-relevant features to OSM and demonstrating a template for organized mapping campaigns in risk zones.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates how open geospatial science and community engagement can improve urban disaster resilience. The routing model is a bridge between science and practice, showing that open data and open tools together can overcome resource gaps in Global South cities. Governments and citizens gain reliable maps and decision-support tools at no extra cost, contributing to both the OSM community and disaster preparedness.

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